

Exploring seismic fragility and strengthening of masonry built heritage in Lisbon (Portugal) via the Applied Element Method

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ABSTRACT

Although mainland Portugal has been spared from large magnitude earthquakes in recent years, it faces a threat due to the presence of several active fault systems. In such a framework, Portuguese pre-code masonry construction is believed to be the most vulnerable in the existing building stock. Given the lack of information on earthquake damage to this stock, the use of detailed numerical models is a viable strategy to comprehend its seismic behavior. This paper provides an updated fragility characterization of Lisbon pre-code masonry buildings based on their seismic assessment through the Applied Element Method. To limit the computational time, a promising pushover strategy, known as Incremental Ground Acceleration, was adopted. After the characterization of the current fragility, two retrofit layouts based on piers strengthening were modeled and assessed for the building stock whose seismic capacity does not meet expected demand. The aim of the paper is to derive updated fragility curves for the Lisbon region to support risk analysis incorporating the latest hazard studies and to offer insights into potential retrofit interventions.

1. Introduction

Fragility curves play an important role in seismic risk studies by providing the likelihood of a structure to reach a certain level of damage due to earthquakes. This probability is influenced by the unpredictability of seismic ground motion and structure response. Fragility curves could belong to four main categories [1–6]: (i) empirical, derived through on post-earthquake damage observations [7–11]; (ii) expert judgement, if the relationship between the damage and the seismic intensity level is given based on expert opinion [12]; (iii) analytical, derived from numerical strategies based on mechanical models (e.g., rigid body model) or non-linear analyses [13–17]; (iv) hybrid, when some of previous methods are combined [18–20].

Although mainland Portugal has not been the target of large magnitude earthquakes in recent years, its geographical location makes it susceptible, as evidenced by historical events such as the devastating 1755 Lisbon earthquake ($M_w = 8.5$), 1909 Benavente earthquake ($M_w = 6.3$) and the 1969 Algarve earthquake ($M_w = 7.8$). The seismic events caused extensive damage, especially in masonry constructions [21]. Furthermore, no seismic design has been considered until the first Portuguese regulation emerged in RSCCS 1958 [22].

The present study aims to develop analytical fragility curves based

on the results obtained from numerical analyses conducted using the Applied Element Method (AEM). The analyses are specifically targeted to the pre-code masonry buildings situated in the Metropolitan Area of Lisbon (MAL), which is the region in Portugal with the highest seismic risk [23–25]. These studies developed fragility and vulnerability functions to characterize the building stock essentially based on statistical data and expert opinion, along with empirical methods. Other studies were recently developed for the region of Lisbon based on numerical models, emphasizing the high vulnerability of masonry buildings to moderate seismic intensity levels, amongst which the following are highlighted: Milosevic, Cattari and Bento 2020 [26] and Simões et al., 2020 [27] developed fragility curves for typical prototypes of pre-code masonry buildings in the Lisbon region accounting for the uncertainty in the material properties. Their study considered a range of scaled response spectra compatible with the seismic action defined in [28] (Portuguese version of Eurocode 8 – EC8–3) for a 475-year return period. Bernardo et al., 2022 [16] derived fragility curves and time-based vulnerability functions for seismic assessment in compliance with EC8–3, considering a large synthetic database of representative buildings to couple with uncertainty in both materials and geometry.

The present study considers the database of representative buildings for the region of Lisbon [16] and derives fragility curves compatible

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Fig. 1. Benchmarking AEM against EFM: capacity curves and failure configurations derived from pushover analyses according to uniform load (top) and triangular load (bottom) distributions.

Fig. 2. AEM models of archetypes A1, A3, B2, C1, C3 with 3 stories high.

Table 1
Statistical properties for the geometric parameters [57].

Parameters	L_x [m]	L_y [m]	IWD [-]	H_0 [m]	H_n [m]	OR_F [-]	OR_B [-]	Th_1 [m]	Th_2 [m]	Th_3 [m]	Th_4 [m]
Value	12.6	12.1	0.054	3.00	3.01	0.23	0.21	0.47	0.34	0.21	0.14

Note: L_x and L_y – building in plan dimensions; IWD – interior walls density; H_0 and H_n – ground and upper floor stories height; OR – openings ratio: front (OR_F) and back (OR_B) façade; Th – walls thickness: main façades (1), lateral façades (2), inner (3), partition (4)

with more recent PSHA studies [29]. Detailed tridimensional numerical models were built and analyzed via the Applied Element Method (AEM), through Incremental Ground Acceleration (IGA) [30,31]. The response of the structures was computed for different hazard quantiles and return periods to evaluate the dispersion in demand. Based on the results obtained, the buildings with higher vulnerability were retrofitted and the

corresponding fragility curves updated, for which a consistent improvement of seismic performance was found. The integration of fragility curves with the retrofit adopted is useful to support risk studies and enhance the resilience of structures against earthquake-induced damage.

Table 2
Material properties (MP) of masonry – outer (Out) and inner (Int) walls.

Masonry set	Mechanical properties													
	E [GPa]		G [GPa]		f_c [MPa]		τ_0 [MPa]		f_t [MPa]		Friction [-]		w [kN/m ³]	
	Out	Int	Out	Int	Out	Int	Out	Int	Out	Int	Out	Int	Out	Int
MP1	5.6	2.2	2.38	0.91	7.00	2.80	0.21	0.21	0.315	0.315	0.8	0.8	1.8	1.2
MP2	4.0	1.6	1.70	0.65	5.00	2.00	0.15	0.15	0.225	0.225	0.8	0.8	1.8	1.2
MP3	3.0	1.3	1.28	0.55	3.75	1.63	0.11	0.11	0.165	0.165	0.8	0.8	1.8	1.2
MP4	2.0	1.0	0.85	0.45	2.50	1.25	0.07	0.07	0.105	0.105	0.8	0.8	1.8	1.2
MP5	0.8	0.4	0.34	0.18	1.00	0.5	0.03	0.03	0.042	0.042	0.8	0.8	1.8	1.2

Note: E – Young's modulus, G – shear modulus, f_c – compressive strength, τ_0 – cohesion, f_t – tensile strength, Friction – tangent value of friction angle, w – density.

Table 3
Properties assumed for retrofit layer (mortar and fibers as a whole), based on Bernardo et al., 2019 [42].

Property	E [GPa]	G [GPa]	Yield stress [MPa]	τ_0 [MPa]	Ultimate stress [MPa]	Friction [-]	Ultimate strain [-]	w [kN/m ³]
Retrofit layer	15	6.5	2.5	0.21	3.83	0.8	0.2	1.85

Table 4
Properties assumed for retrofit-to-masonry interface, based on Bernardo et al., 2019 [42].

Connection	E [GPa]	G [GPa]	f_c [MPa]	τ_0 [MPa]	f_t [MPa]	Friction [-]
Retrofit-to-masonry interface	4.0	1.6	4.65	0	0.465	0.8

2. The use of AEM for the modeling of URM structures

Discontinuous strategies have proved to be effective for the simulation of existing masonry components [32,33]. In such a framework, promising findings were found through the use of the AEM. The method is based on the discretization of structures using rigid blocks, connected by a series of nonlinear springs whose behavior is based on material laws assigned, until a certain separation-strain threshold is reached [34,35].

The capability of AEM for simulating masonry components has been validated at pier scale, reduced- and full- building scales. Malomo et al., 2018 [36] benchmarked the in-plane behavior against three calcium-silicate brick masonry piers derived from Dutch typologies, subjected to shear-compression cyclic tests. Micro-modeling technique of masonry texture according to [37] was adopted, implementing both bricks and mortar properties. A satisfactory matching between experimental and numerical outcomes was found in terms of energy dissipation, crack pattern and drift value. The benchmarking of calcium-silicate masonry was extended to full scale shaking-table tests in Malomo et al., 2020 [38]. Khattak et al., 2023 [39] benchmarked AEM for the simulation of in-plane (IP) and out-of-plane (OOP) behaviors of stone and brick masonry, based on an U-shaped test carried out in the LNEC facilities [40]. It was found that the tool is capable of simulating such behaviors also in the nonlinear dynamic range, although an over-estimation of displacements was found for lower intensities of motion. Bernardo et al., 2022 [41] discussed the simulation of masonry aggregate buildings through AEM, once their properties were calibrated against pier-scale cyclic tests and modal behavior based on Ambient Vibration Tests (AVT). A discretization procedure based on homogeneous masonry properties was used, with a regular block mesh (so-called *normal* in the framework of [37]), on the contrary to micro-modeling in [36,38,39].

The potential of AEM for the simulation of URM retrofit techniques was also assessed. Bernardo et al., 2019 [42] modeled a double-jacketing intervention based on hydraulic mortar NHL 3.5 with glass fiber-reinforced polymers, linked to URM substrate via 7 cm-long plastic connectors with 40 cm and 50 cm spacing, along horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. AEM was able to reproduce the behavior of both bare and retrofitted specimens in terms of displacement and force capacities, i.e., the envelope of experimental hysteretic cycles.

Moreover, Adhikari and D'Ayala 2020 [43] showed that AEM can be successfully used for the study of heritage masonry structures. Rubble stone masonry samples derived by masonry textures surveyed in Nepal were tested and calibrated, adopting a micro-modeling strategy with triangular-based parallelepiped, which simulate both i) failure of units through sub-elements and ii) failure of units-to-units interfaces. A similar strategy was also applied of the simulation of confined clay brick masonry [31].

3. Numerical modeling of Lisbon masonry buildings

3.1. Modelling strategy and assumptions

The structural models have been constructed according to the numerical AEM strategy in the Extreme Loading for Structures (ELS) software implementation [44], which has proved to be effective and efficient for the simulation of unreinforced masonry structures (Section 2).

The structural components are discretized through rigid blocks, with nonlinearity lumped at interface springs.

Linear normal k_n and shear stiffness k_s are derived from Young's modulus E , shear modulus G , contact area A and block height (perpendicular to contact surface) as per Eqs. (1) and (2), according to [34].

$$k_n = \frac{EA}{h} \quad (1)$$

$$k_s = \frac{GA}{h} \quad (2)$$

A meso-modeling homogeneous discretization strategy [41,45–47] was adopted for masonry components, with pseudo-cubic 8-noded rigid blocks of average 0.3 m size and the generation of 5×5 (i.e., 25) nonlinear springs per each contact surface, according to [34,36,38]. The size of the blocks was derived by a previous study [41], where a mesh convergence analysis was carried out for a similar building typology. The nonlinear behavior of masonry vertical structures is described through the Concrete Maekawa model [48], assuming a pseudo-parabolic compressive envelope and a tension cut-off, and the Mohr-Coulomb yielding model for shear. Once the threshold separation strain is reached, material springs are deleted and contact springs are

Fig. 3. Capacity curves for archetypes A1, A3, B2, C1, and C3, with 3, 4 and 5 stories high, for X longitudinal direction, with markers for LS1 (green square), LS2 (yellow triangle), LS3 (orange diamond), LS4 (red circle).

generated [49].

Diaphragms and lintel elements were modeled through linear brittle models in tension and compression, although no material failures were expected (and also detected in the postprocessing of results). Rigid floor diaphragms is a common typology in the MAL region and evaluated in previous case studies, high vulnerability to moderate and high seismicity levels was found [16,26,41].

3.2. Validation of the modeling strategy

Advanced numerical tools such as AEM, although promising in replicating with good approximation the behavior of structural elements, require a detailed characterization of material laws and mechanical parameters. As an example, the estimation of the shear stiffness of the springs may be tricky in the framework of masonry discontinuous models, since ratios varying from 1.0 to 0.5 of the normal stiffness are commonly found in literature, e.g., 1.0 [50], 0.55 [51,52], 0.5 [45], 0.29

Fig. 4. Capacity curves for archetypes A1, A3, B2, C1, and C3, with 3, 4 and 5 stories high, for Y transverse direction, with markers for LS1 (green square), LS2 (yellow triangle), LS3 (orange diamond), LS4 (red circle).

[53].

Based on the validation framework for AEM models provided in [47], the AEM models were firstly validated through the benchmarking of capacity curves against the ones obtained from a previous study for the same building's typology employing the Equivalent Frame Model (EFM) in the TreMuri research software [54]. The previous calibration of EFM models, based on cyclic experimental tests performed on some masonry panels with the mean material properties adopted [42], is discussed in [41]. In the scope of this work, AEM tridimensional models starting from

the mean material properties and geometry were built. To cover the uncertainty in both geometry and materials [16], a probabilistic framework to represent the building stock in the area under investigation was conducted. Therefore, the set of material properties selected, corresponding to the different quantiles of [16], intends to reflect their influence in the buildings global response, providing a scatter for the limit states defined and the values of PGA demand. The results were used to derive fragility curves for the building stock.

Hence, for benchmarking purposes, pushover analyses were carried

Table 5

Maximum crack width of masonry components measured in function of Limit States and comparison with some reference studies.

Stories	Crack width [mm] and (Coefficient of Variation [-])			
	LS1	LS2 = DS	LS3 = SD	LS4 =NC
1	0.52 (0.63)	0.97 (0.44)	6.97 (0.86)	14.04 (0.82)
2	0.93 (0.13)	1.32 (0.16)	9.82 (0.85)	12.62 (0.79)
3	1.16 (0.17)	1.62 (0.19)	10.23 (0.83)	13.16 (0.74)
4	1.46 (0.16)	1.89 (0.16)	10.83 (0.84)	12.28 (0.75)
5	1.54 (0.15)	2.04 (0.18)	11.16 (0.85)	13.22 (0.67)
Average	1.12	1.57	9.80	13.06
Adhikari and D'Ayala 2020; Adhikari 2021[43,56]	1	5	10	> 10
Giardina et al., 2013[67]	≤ 1	≤ 5	5 –15	15 –25

out for both AEM and EFM, i.e., ELS and TreMuri, according to triangular and uniform load distributions along the height of the building. The average displacement of roof was assumed as the control point. The obtained base shear-displacement capacity curves and failure configurations are reported in Fig. 1, labelled as AEM and TREMURI. The comparison reveals a good agreement between the two strategies, with similar nonlinear envelope and peak shear force, with a slight overestimation of the ultimate displacement of AEM compared to EFM. In order to match the outcomes of TreMuri, the input shear modulus in ELS had to be reduced through a 0.8 multiplier with respect to original formulation given in (Eq. (2)). The ratio between shear and normal springs stiffnesses found was hence equal to 0.32. The AEM model was then considered calibrated.

Finally, in the scope of the present work, Incremental Ground Acceleration (IGA) analyses [30,31,41,43] were carried out by giving an horizontal increasing acceleration at the ground. The effectiveness of this strategy in predicting the seismic behavior of masonry structures has been benchmarked against Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) in [56], where IGA was proven to be capable of predicting the capacity curves with higher accuracy than conventional pushover load distributions. IGA capacity curves were found closer to uniform-derived than triangular-derived capacity curves, with a slightly higher maximum base shear force (less than 20 % difference) (Fig. 1).

3.3. Geometrical layouts, material properties and boundary conditions

The geometric features (i.e., plan layout, stories height, openings ratio, walls thickness and floor type) were statistically obtained based on a population of 100 pre-code buildings (built before 1960s), as described in [16,57]. From the nine archetypes derived in [16], five were selected for this study, namely A1, A3, B2, C1, C3, considering different material and geometrical properties, up to 5 stories high. Fig. 2 presents the layout of these archetypes for 3 stories high. Table 1 summarizes the geometrical parameters and value adopted for the archetypes. Based on the mean size configuration of B2 archetype (12.6×12.1 m), the remaining four archetypes were derived assuming a dispersion equals to one standard deviation, i.e., the length of longitudinal façades parallel to X axis $L_x = 12.6 \pm 5.0$ m and the length of transverse façades parallel to Y axis $L_y = 12.1 \pm 4.1$ m. The total in plan area ranges approximately between 60.0 m^2 and 285.0 m^2 . The mean thickness values for the façade walls were assumed, whilst for the inner walls the mode (i.e., most common) values were adopted (representative of more than 60 % of the buildings surveyed according to [57]).

The definition of material mechanical properties was based on the wide range of properties selected in [16], where property uncertainties were taken into account through Monte Carlo simulations (MCS). In order to decrease the computational time of AEM analyses, five different percentiles (10 %, 16 %, 50 %, 84 % and 90 %) of the material properties (MP) sampled were extracted from the previous MCS to cover the variability considered. Table 2 depicts masonry properties (MP) MP1 to MP5 corresponding to very good, good, medium, low and very low MP, respectively. Masonry material was assumed as a homogeneous medium, with equivalent material properties. The mean macroscopic mechanical parameters adopted, namely the Young's modulus E and shear modulus G , were derived using a strain-based first-order homogenization technique applied to the properties of small representative specimens and obtained from laboratory destructive tests. Further details can be found in Krejčí et al. 2021 [58] and Bernardo et al., 2022 [41].

Floor diaphragms were modelled using 12 cm-thick rigid blocks and springs, with Young's modulus E of 30 GPa and shear modulus G of 13 GPa, as derived for the Lisbon stock in [16]. Timber lintels above openings were modeled through rigid blocks and springs as well, according to [38]. C14 timber mechanical properties were assumed, as per [47], since no detailed characterization is available and the elements are not expected to exceed linear behavior. The adopted properties include a Young's modulus E of 7000 MPa and shear modulus G of 440 MPa, tensile strength f_t of 10 MPa and density of 350 kg/m^3 . The wall thickness was adopted for the lintel, together with a height equal to 15 cm and a support length (i.e., length of lateral insertion inside the wall)

Fig. 5. Crack pattern for B2P3 model and MP3 material properties set, for the main limit states. Crack width thresholds corresponding to LS1 (green), LS2 (yellow), LS3 (orange), LS4 (red), as per Table 5.

Fig. 6. Capacity curves for archetypes A3, B2, and C1, with 3, 4 and 5 stories high, for X longitudinal direction, in function of retrofit layout. Markers for LS1 (green square), LS2 (yellow triangle), LS3 (orange diamond), LS4 (red circle).

equal to 15 cm.

The floor-to-wall interfaces were assumed equal to floor ones, in order to guarantee a good connection with respect to masonry properties (i.e., failure was expected on wall side and not at interface) and ensure equal planar displacements. The interfaces between the various masonry walls and masonry-to-lintels were assumed equal to the outer wall properties, different for each masonry set.

The model was considered fixed at the base in all degrees of freedom.

Masonry permanent loads were calculated through distributed density assigned. Diaphragms permanent loads were equal to 3.78 kN/m², while live loads equal to 2.0 kN/m² were assumed for category A (residential use) [59]. The adopted seismic load combination was considered, as per [60].

3.4. Choice and modeling of the strengthening intervention

A wide range of techniques are available for the retrofit of masonry structures, based on units texture and design [61,62]. When masonry is sound and monolithic behavior can be assumed, the application of composite strips (polymer matrix with fibers) onto wall surfaces is an effective method to enhance their tensile and shear strength [63]. Composites have gained widespread recognition in the retrofitting and conservation of built heritage, attributed to their favorable strength-to-weight ratio and ease of application. It is advisable, however, to install them with compatible mortars rather than resins, ensuring more reversible and durable interventions [64–66]. This type of intervention is currently widespread among professional practice and

Fig. 6. (continued).

common retrofit interventions of existing buildings. To this intervention type belongs the one provided in [42], which has been tested on masonry specimens representative of the built stock investigated in this paper. For this reason, such technique was chosen as reference to be simulated in this study.

The strengthening intervention to archetypes consists in the application of the retrofit layer to the outer façades, addressed at improving their IP resistance. The OOP retrofitting is not considered since the box-like behavior of the archetypes was already guaranteed in the bare layout, preventing OOP mechanisms from triggering.

The strengthening solution adopted comprises a double-jacketing retrofit with mortar based on hydraulic lime NHL 3.5 and fiberglass mesh, with total thickness of 3 cm (2 cm for the leveling layer + 1 cm for the finishing layer). The mesh was fixed to the masonry using plastic connectors, approximately 7 cm long, in a grid pattern of 40 cm width

by 50 cm height. The solution was evaluated through experimental cyclic tests and used to calibrate the AEM formulation as described in [42].

In this study, retrofit was applied to façades parallel to X direction, since such archetypes for MP4 and MP5 properties were found the most vulnerable (see Section 3.3). Furthermore, two layouts were assessed, with retrofit in both outer and inner sides of façades (2S), and only in the inner sides of façades (1S). The former technique was assessed since the Portuguese historical building represented by the archetypes are often subjected to conservation laws which limit alterations of their outer aesthetics. It follows that complete (2S) retrofit of piers could be challenging or forbidden. The retrofit layer was modeled through 3 cm-thick blocks, with main dimensions equal to underneath masonry mesh. Retrofit and retrofit-to-wall springs were modeled as per [42], with properties listed in Table 3 and Table 4.

Fig. 7. Metropolitan Area of Lisbon (left) and seismic hazard curves for different return periods (right).

Table 6

Gutenberg-Richter parameters and attenuation laws adopted.

Seismogenic model	a	b	m_{\max}	Attenuation laws
EC8	2.41	0.71	7.2	Ambraseys et al. 1996[72]
ERSTA	3.03	0.79	7.1	Atkinson and Boore 2006[73]
SERA	3.95	1.00	7.4	Akkar and Bommer 2010[74]

Note: a is the intercept and b the slope of the logarithmic relationship between the number of earthquakes and their magnitudes. m_{\max} is the maximum magnitude of the truncated Gutenberg-Richter law.

4. Seismic behavior of URM archetypes

4.1. Bare archetypes

The outcomes of IGA-based pushover analyses are reported in this Section. The displacement capacity was assumed as the average of the values of top floor elements, while the shear was measured at the base up to reaching 20 % decay of the maximum peak strength (Near Collapse limit state – NC), as provided by the EC8–3 [28] for a global safety verification. The definition of limit states follows the provisions of EC8–3 [28], namely Damage Limitation (DL-LS2), Significant Damage (SD-LS3) and Near Collapse (NC-LS4). Additionally, Immediate Occupancy limit state (LS1) was also considered and assumed equal to 70 % of the displacement for LS2.

The capacity curves normalized in terms of spectral acceleration S_a and spectral displacement S_d , and the corresponding limit states, for the archetypes A1, A3, B2, C1 and C3, with 3 to 5 stories high are presented in Fig. 3, for X longitudinal direction, and Fig. 4, for Y transverse direction. The S_a values generally decrease when the number of stories and the material properties increase. For the X direction, the highest S_a is detected for C archetypes with longer façades along X direction ($L_x > L_y$), with beneficial effects of lower masses (C1 archetype).

The capacity curves derived by medium size B2 archetype showed a different behavior compared to others, based on horizontal acceleration along X or Y direction. For Y direction (Fig. 4), B2 capacity curves were mainly placed in the average of the group, with A3 the upper bound, due to the highest L_y with highest L_y -on-mass ratio, and C1 the lower bound, due to lowest L_y -on-mass ratio. Since the transverse façades do not have openings, the resisting shear mechanisms were directly proportional to L_y . Instead, for the X direction (Fig. 3), the highest density of openings in the façades made the increase of capacity not directly proportional to

length L_x , with C1 the upper bound and A3 the lower bound, due to highest and lowest L_x -on-mass ratio. However, B2 outcomes were generally closer to lower bounds A1 and A3, although some variations were found based on number of floors and property set.

The displacement capacity was found higher for taller specimens. Low variability at archetype varying was found for X-direction capacity curves, although the dispersion increases when mechanical properties are scarce (Fig. 3). Higher variability was observed for Y-direction capacity curves, due to their dependance on wide piers. Such behavior also affected displacement limit states, with higher variability detected in Y direction than X, especially for LS4.

Based on the strain diagrams corresponding to each Limit State, the maximum tensile crack widths on main façades were obtained, as reported in Table 5. The values found for the single-story layouts had the greatest discrepancy from the other stories ones, likely related to the lower capacity to redistribute seismic forces over the walls after local failures. Variation was lower from two- to five-stories instead. The dispersion of crack width values increased as damage status becomes more severe. A comparison with other crack width assumptions per limit state is also given in Table 5. Values derived from AEM modeling were found close to ones discussed in [43,56,67], although they were slightly higher for LS1 and lower for LS2.

As per collapse shape, damage is lumped at the first floor. A representative incremental crack pattern for archetype B2P3 and MP3 material set, accounting seismic action along X direction, is shown in Fig. 5. Cracks appeared in the first-floor walls at LS1, growing larger and spreading to the second floor by LS2. Upon reaching LS3, shear cracks raised in the piers of the first floor, while horizontal cracks developed at the base of the transverse façades due to hinge formation. Finally, at LS4, severe shear cracks grew along the entire section of the piers on the first floor, with the crack pattern in the transverse walls extending further.

4.2. Retrofitted archetypes - MP4 and MP5 properties

The outcomes of IGAs carried out for the five retrofitted archetypes, with properties MP4 and MP5, are discussed in this Section. Capacity curves were derived as per bare buildings discussed in Section 4.1. Figure 6 illustrates the capacity curves normalized in terms of spectral acceleration S_a and spectral displacement S_d , and the corresponding limit states, for the archetypes A3, B2, and C1, with 3 to 5 stories high are presented in Fig. 6, for X longitudinal direction.

The outcomes showed that 2S retrofit was effective in increasing shear capacity (i.e., spectral acceleration), especially when the masonry

Fig. 8. Seismic performance points for 475-years return period in terms of global drift (top) and spectral acceleration (bottom) in longitudinal (left) and transverse (right) direction. Dash-lines correspond to the mean results by archetypes.

properties were lower (MP5), whereas it improved the displacement capacity when URM characteristics were better (MP4).

The introduction of 1S retrofit enabled the increase of the bare archetypes' capacity, although reduced if compared to full two-sided one. In particular, the gap between the two strengthening techniques increased when $L_x \geq L_y$ (see B2 and C1 in Fig. 6), whereas it was more limited when $L_x \leq L_y$, e.g., A3.

Upon the introduction of the retrofit, the decrease of S_a at number of floors increasing became more evident, although the failure mechanism at first story was almost unchanged.

5. Seismic fragility-based assessment

This Section presents the vulnerability curves of the archetypes and evaluates the retrofit efficiency for the various prototypes.

5.1. Seismic hazard characterization

The seismic activity in Portugal manifests in two distinct scenarios: offshore (interplate) and inland (intraplate) events. Previous studies have pointed out that intraplate scenarios are the causes for major losses in the MAL region, mainly occurred in the Lower Tagus Valley Fault (LTVF) (Fig. 7). For this reason, only the region integrating the LTVF was considered in the seismic hazard analysis. The seismic action was assessed using the hazard curves at ground surface derived from the classical probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA). The computation of the PSHA was performed in the OpenQuake engine platform [68,69] by considering the area-source seismogenic model adopted in the

development of the Portuguese National Annex of Eurocode 8 [70] and two recent studies, namely the Seismic and Tsunami Risk in Algarve (ERSTA) [71] and the Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research (SERA) project [29]. The attenuation laws for the seismic ground motion were considered in terms of spectral acceleration (0.01 to 4.0 s) at bedrock [72–74]. The seismogenic models and attenuation laws were combined in a logic-tree with equal weight. Table 6 summarizes the Gutenberg-Richter parameters to describe the magnitude-frequency of the events and the attenuation laws adopted.

Fig. 7 shows the response spectrum for the 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles for different return periods RP (years) = {25, 50, 100, 250; 475, 975, 1100, 2500, 5000} and computed from the PSHA at every site (parish), accounting the spatial variability of the seismic ground motion in the MAL region. The median values achieved are in line in the current version of the EC8–1 [75], namely in terms of maximum amplitude of spectral acceleration (~ 0.17 g) in the period range of approximately 0.1 s - 0.3 s. Note that, it was only considered the inland scenario, which is characterized by higher energy content in the high frequencies and short duration.

5.2. Seismic demand for performance-based assessment

The seismic performance assessment of the previous prototypes was estimated through the improved Capacity Spectrum Method outlined in FEMA-440 [76]. Fig. 8 depicts the seismic performance of the database analyzed for the 475-years return period and median hazard quantile, in function of masonry properties MPs and stories number (from one-story P1 to five-story P5). The values of global drift (taken as the EDP) in the

Fig. 9. Vulnerability curves for B2 archetype (3, 4 and 5 stories) in longitudinal direction as a function of global drift (EDP) and IM (PGA): 50th (top) and 84th (bottom) hazard. Dashed line corresponds to the Significant Damage limit state.

longitudinal direction, i.e., parallel to the main façades, tend to increase with the number of interior walls and stories, in archetypes with narrow façades (A1 and A3). The opposite occurred in terms of spectral acceleration (EDP) since the ratio of masonry walls area to floor area in plan is similar between archetypes and the main contribution of the buildings capacity is given by the façades walls. The archetype B2 also seems to represent the mean performance of the structure in terms of both EDP considered, at least for the 475 years return period. For the transversal direction, archetypes with longer side walls (A3 and C3) reach higher values of spectral acceleration and lower global drift values, as expected, since the performance in this direction is mainly governed by the side walls behavior. Note that, these conclusions also seem to be more evident as the material properties (MP) are lower, since for a good MP all the archetypes seem to behave in the elastic range for the hazard level considered.

Following the above methodology, the response of the database was computed for different return periods (see Section 5.1) and the performance evaluated in terms of global drift (EDP). Fig. 9 shows the relationship between the IM (taken as the PGA) and the global drift (EDP) as a function of archetypes, number of stories and MPs. The results are presented for 50th and 84th hazard quantile. For each MP-indexed structure, a power law function was best fitted to the performance points to describe the functional IM-EDP relationship. Since these curves describe the structures performance for increasing levels of intensity, they can also be interpreted as time-based vulnerability curves serving multiple purposes such as seismic safety assessment, fragility analysis

and risk studies.

In the scope of this study, these results were addressed to convert the limit states (capacity) into IM and derive fragility curves depicted in the Section 5.3. For instance, Fig. 9 also shows the SD limit state (horizontal dashed-lines) – usually adopted by the codes for the seismic verification of current buildings – and can be easily linked to the values of PGA-capacity. Similarly, the values of PGA-demand can also be converted in terms of global drift and compared with capacity to support safety assessment.

5.3. Seismic fragility assessment

Fragility curves discussed in this section give the conditional probability that a certain limit state is exceeded for a given IM value, herein defined in terms of PGA. Fragility curves should be derived from empirical data to best fit the sample analyzed; however, this requires a large amount of data do be statistically significant. Therefore, fragility curves were derived by assuming a lognormal cumulative distribution function (e.g., [55,77]), with mean PGA values corresponding to the limit state of Damage Limitation (DL), Significant Damage (SD) and Near Collapse (NC). Standard deviation (β_D) of the natural logarithm was estimated from the error between the analytical function fitted and the empirical data in Fig. 9. The β_D values (50th hazard quantile) varied between 0.30 and 0.85. In addition to these values, the dispersion of the capacity (β_C) was considered, which varies between 0.17 to 0.76 (DL), 0.20 to 0.76 (SD), and 0.30 to 0.60 (NC). The total dispersion β_T was

Fig. 10. Fragility curves (3, 4 and 5 stories) for the 50th material quantile: 50th (top) and 84th (bottom) hazard.

computed by square root of the sum of squares, accounting for both uncertainties independently. Based on this assumption, the following analytical expression for the fragility is presented, that can be interpreted as the probability of reaching or exceeding a given Damage State (DS) for a certain seismic intensity measure (IM) defined in terms of PGA.

$$P(DS_i | IM = PGA) = \Phi \left[\frac{1}{\beta_T} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{PGA}{PGA_{DS_i}} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show the fragility curves for the combination of 50th and 84th PSHA with 50th and 16th MP, respectively.

Analyzing the results for the 475-years return period and median MP, it can be concluded that the probability of structures being at slight damage (DL) can reach around 30 % (50th PSHA) and 60 % (84th PSHA), while the probability of moderate and severe damage (SD and NC) is around 12 % (50th PSHA) and 30 % (84th PSHA). Assuming the 16th quantile lower bound for the MP, the expected damage can reach up to 50 % (50th PSHA) and 70 % (84th PSHA) for DL, and 40 % (50th PSHA) and 50 % (84th PSHA). For the PGA level analyzed, the probability of reaching the SD and NC limit states seems to be lower for archetypes with higher L_x (C1 and C3), since the main resistance of these structures are governed by the main façades, while the highest vulnerability is attributed to archetypes with narrow façades. It is important to emphasize that these results were derived considering the mean hazard in the MAL region; hence, higher seismicity levels are expected in certain regions. Moreover, the influence of soil may also amplify the structural

response in situ and the expected damage.

Considering the previous results, the retrofit solution described in Section 3.4 was applied at one-side (1S) and two-side (2S) of the main façades of MP4 and MP5 buildings, since they were found the most vulnerable typologies. Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 depict the related fragility curves and the comparison with the bare structural state. The results are only presented for the 84th hazard quantile, since it is also intended to cover the coexistence of buildings with poor material properties located in most of MAL regions with highest seismicity. The strengthening effect on in-plane damage reduction is more efficient for the 2S retrofit, as expected. Comparing the results for the PGA value of around 0.22 g for the median archetype in the MAL region (B2 with three stories height), it can be noticed that the damage reduction is around (MP4|MP5): DL – 6 %|5 % (1S) and 22 %|20 % (2S); SD – 12 %|6 % (1S) and 50 %|51 % (2S); NC – 60 %|62 % (1S) and 90 %|74 % (2S). Also, the influence of the strengthening solution seems to be more effective for PGA demand values that exceed the elastic capacity, herein defined by the DL. In general, this finding is more evident as the building height decreases, especially for MP5. Naturally, the application of the retrofit in typologies with similar mass, for instance A3 and C1, results in a higher efficiency for the latter, since the improvements in the capacity and/or ductility increases as the plan aspect ratio is higher in the retrofitted direction.

6. Final comments and conclusions

The objective of this paper is to provide updated fragility curves for

Fig. 11. Fragility curves (3, 4 and 5 stories) for the 16th material quantile: 50th (top) and 84th (bottom) hazard.

the Lisbon region at bedrock, incorporating the latest hazard studies, and to offer insights into possible retrofit interventions. The results provided in the manuscript can be linked to the URM building stock in the Metropolitan Area of Lisbon, since the database used to derive the geometry of the representative models and the material properties included a comprehensive survey [57] on the population of these structures and their structural response corresponding to the local seismicity in that area. Based on this information, five archetypes were extracted from the original database representing the median, upper and lower bound geometrical layouts. The materials adopted (MP1 to MP5) followed various quantiles of the original distributions to cover the wide range of properties. Considering this set of prototypes, the numerical models were built using the Applied Element Method (AEM) formulation and following subjected to Incremental Ground Accelerations (IGAs) to estimate their seismic capacity. The outcomes of the analyses revealed a box-like behavior of the archetypes investigated, so that out-of-plane mechanisms were inhibited, and the seismic capacity of the building was ruled by the in-plane shear behavior of piers parallel to earthquake direction. Limit states were defined within the global capacity curves and correlated with the maximum tensile crack widths obtained from damage pattern observations. Incorporating these findings into damageability functions will enable expressing damage into losses in further risk studies.

The seismic action at bedrock was derived from PSHA, combining different seismogenic regions in a logic tree event, including the updated European hazard model. The seismic hazard level covered a wide range

of return periods to derive the relationship between the seismic response of the structures and Intensity Measure (IM), herein defined in terms of global drift and PGA, respectively. These curves, the so-called time-based vulnerability curves, allowed to compute the dispersion in seismic demand and evaluate the most vulnerable structures for a code compliance with 475-year return period.

The analysis of outcomes for a 475-year return period and median properties MP3 suggests that there is a probability of structures in the bare state to experience slight damage (DL) ranging from 30 % to 60 %, while severe damage (SD) probability is around 12 % to 30 %. Considering a lower bound quantile for the MP, expected slight damage (DL) ranges from 50 % to 70 % and more severe damage (SD) up to 40 % to 50 %.

Based on the results obtained, two retrofit layouts, consisting of in-plane strengthening of main façades, were considered. The side walls were not retrofitted for out-of-plane mechanisms, as box-like behavior prevented them from triggering. Consequently, their performance was contingent upon that of the main façades. The most vulnerable typologies, namely those with MP4 and MP5 property sets, were assessed, encompassing both outer and inner sides of façades, and exclusively inner sides.

The damage reduction varied as a function of the limit states: DL ranged from 5 % to 22 %, SD from 6 % to 51 %, and NC from 60 % to 90 %, from the least improvement of one-sided strengthening to larger benefit provided by two-sided one.

The fragility curves obtained can be employed in risk studies, also in

Fig. 12. Fragility curves with retrofit (3, 4 and 5 stories) for MP4.

Fig. 13. Fragility curves with retrofit (3, 4 and 5 stories) for MP5.

the framework of a cost-benefit analysis. The outcomes of the retrofit solution adopted also provide relevant information about the estimation of overstrength coefficients and ductility factors to support the safety seismic assessment of in-plane strengthened masonry buildings using code-based approaches.

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Code availability

Not applicable.

Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Paulo B. Lourenço: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Vasco Bernardo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Matteo Salvalaggio:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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